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ABSTRACT BOOK

**HEALTH MANAGEMENT:
MANAGING THE PRESENT
AND SHAPING THE FUTURE**

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Health workforce support needs in the light of COVID crisis (example from Serbia)

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The COVID pandemic revealed all the weaknesses of health systems. Lack of capacity to accommodate patients and lack of appropriate equipment, inadequate organisation of treating non-COVID patients, and numerous challenges along with a large number of deaths have affected all health professionals.

Lots of these challenges were and are monitored and measurable, and measures have been and are being taken according to possibilities. However, significant impacts and changes are changing health professionals personally and professionally, though still not wholly visible and impossible to assess the crisis consequences on health professionals' mental health.

Although a research on the impact of the pandemic on the mental health of the population, patients, and health professionals has already been made, it appears that there are neither enough actions nor the possibility to take action to support health workers.

The paper aims to present an example of the activities taken by the Group Analytic Society Belgrade (DGAB) in the COVID pandemic emergency circumstances. Wishing to support health professionals and associates, and student volunteers, DGAB has organised and created online groups. The setting is defined, participation in the group is open and voluntary, in compliance with confidentiality and non-disclosure principles. The goal of the support group to health professionals is to exchange experiences, feelings, and mutual support in daily work. Online groups thus become a space for connection, understanding and common reflection, therefore influencing the capacity building for health professionals' resilience in the pandemic crisis conditions.

Group leaders are experienced group analysts, members of DGAB. The paper aims to present the challenges and aggravating circumstances in forming groups. A gap between the present need for support and the difficulties to form groups is noticed. The aggravating circumstances to form an online group can be seen as strong resistance in accepting the offered help, i.e. negating the need for support, while experience with health professionals individually indicates a feeling of helplessness and hopelessness, and the impossibility of any help (which can be a projection of the situation in "severely affected" health systems). Moreover, there are real extraordinary circumstances in planning shifts, engagement, and the need to provide time for physical recovery and family time after difficult shifts in the "red zones", in order to temporarily suppress the job-related thoughts. Therefore, it is important to further explore the ways to overcome the noticed resilience, to exchange experiences in providing support to health professionals to ensure the strengthening of human resources capacity and health systems in general.

The pandemic crisis has created the need for a complex approach and support to the most valuable part of the health system, human resources, whether in a COVID or non-COVID system, so health systems could achieve sustainability and overcome the current crisis.